

The Influence of Financial Behavior towards the Household's Financial Stress

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ABSTRACT: The study aimed to determine the influence of financial behavior on household's financial stress in Tagum City, Davao del Norte. This study utilized a quantitative non-experimental, descriptive type of research with 150 respondents selected through purposive sampling technique. Mean was the statistical tool used for the data treatment. Results showed a high financial behavior level and a moderate financial stress level among households in Tagum City. For the students to lower down or avoid experiencing financial stress, they should be concerned enough of their cash flows and investments.

Keywords: *Financial Behavior, Financial Management, Financial Stress, Young Adults of Tagum City, Philippines.*

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Rationale

Generally, many families are still suffering from financial stress (Menard O.,2019). Despite the increase in wages, households face pressure mainly because they still live with lower cash inflow. The household's income is instantly paid to their bills or obligations, and nothing left for their savings (Haslam, D. M., & Burke, K.,2018). Even the higher-earning households report that they also experience financial stress the same with those low-income earners. Moreover, not enough protection and too much debt are the primary reasons why families suffer from financial anxiety (Satter, 2017).

Individuals who are financially stressed may suffer short-term and long-term consequences such as isolation, despair, and depression, which may also be accompanied by a relationship breakdown (Neppl, T. K., Senia, J. M., &Donnellan, M. B.,2016). Often, they cannot live in the usual way because a person might feel hopeless and unimportant. It would cause substance abuse and frequent gambling that can affect household difficulties that commonly impact families. It results in the financial instability of an individual's finances (Jones, Savage & Van Gool, 2014).

Moreover, households that have poor financial behavior and lack of money-related proficiency can prompt helpless life decisions. These decisions can add to financial pressures with unfriendly outcomes. The most exceedingly awful result is vagrancy (Steen & MacKenzie, 2013). In this case, solving this financial issue will give a financial relief among households (Satter, 2017).

In spite of, the researchers have not gone over any study that leads to financial behavior and financial stress among family units in Tagum City. The growing population in the city and the unforeseen struggles of every family who have suffered difficulty handling their finances or have lower literacy, motivate the researchers to pursue this study. The researchers intend to help the community improve their financial behavior, reduce financial stress, and contribute to the community's improvement. Furthermore, the present study shall make a specific contribution and generate new knowledge on households' financial stress. Hence, the primary objectives are to determine the influence of financial behavior on the family unit's financial stress in Tagum City.

1.2 Research objective

The primary purpose of the study is to determine the significant relationship between financial behavior and financial stress among households in Tagum City, precisely; it sought to answer the following sub-objective:

1. To find out the level of financial behavior among households in Tagum City in terms of:
 - 1.1 cash management;
 - 1.2 credit management;
 - 1.3 savings management; and
 - 1.4 investment management.
2. To determine the level of financial stress among households in Tagum City in terms of:
 - 2.1 borrowing money;
 - 2.2 food insecurity; and
 - 2.3 paying bills.
3. To determine if there is a significant relationship between financial behavior and financial stress among households in Tagum City.
4. To ascertain if there are domains of financial behavior that significantly influences financial stress among households in Tagum City.

1.3 Hypothesis

The study's hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance, stating that there is no significant relationship between financial behavior and Financial Stress. Also, there is no domain of financial behavior that significantly influences financial stress among households in Tagum City.

II. Review of Related Literature

This section contains the studies of books, researches, publications, magazines, journals, newspaper and other reliable resources from the internet which supports the analysis of Financial Behavior with its indicators: cash management, credit management, savings management, and investment management (Hilgert, Hogart & Beverly, 2003) and financial stress with its three factors such as borrowing money, food insecurity, and paying bills (Kramer et al. 2019) among Household in Tagum City.

2.1 Financial Behavior

In this present era, financial awareness has awakened the community across the countries (Hilgert and Mogarth, 2013). People want to have stability over their income and consumption over a lifetime. However, it requires good financial behavior or positive actions to get through it. The strategy and awareness of future expectations can influence people's decisions, whether to save or spend. Households that plan for their future always have an upbeat personality on keeping and managing their income appropriately, planning to ensure the family's financial future (Rehman, Sullan & Yemen, 2011). As mentioned above, better financial decisions highlight favorable financial behavior in terms of managing: *cash, credits, saving, and investment* (Hilgert, Hogart& Beverly, 2003).

The most critical aspect of a family's financial management is managing, planning, evaluating, and implementing its cash inflow or income in meeting their financial goals. Mostly, insurance, investment, retirement, and estate planning are not focused, and most households have limited cash inflows (Attanasio, O. & Brugiavini, A., 2003). Therefore, the crucial part of managing cash is through proper budgeting to avoid impulsive spending. Cash can be broken down into non-discretionary or discretionary spending. Non-discretionary spending is those items you need to survive, such as money paid on rent, mortgage payments, heat, lights, gasoline, car payments, etc. At the same time, discretionary spending is spent on entertainment, communication, restaurants, take-out food, food not necessary to survive, vacations, clothing over the minimum, and other luxury items (Hilgert & Mogarth, 2013; Godwin & Koonce, 2010). Moreover, budgeting can help an individual make the most of their living (Irby, 2018).

The Influence of Financial Behavior towards the Household's Financial Stress

On the contrary, by collecting obligations without managing money, a family may superfluously enter a monetary emergency (Robb, C. & Woodyard, A., 2011). For example, low average earners regularly face planning and budgetary administration troublesome when living with obligation or credit duties. Their requirements likewise restricted their capacity to meet their present budgetary responsibilities or dodge further credit utilization to meet everyday needs (Cox, Drew, and Walter, 2010). On the other hand, saving money can uplift the financial security of a person or a household. When a person accumulates massive debt and has a deficit with his/her salary, savings can be a good thing to solve some financial problems and bad debts. Even for some emergencies, concurrences, and fortuitous events, savings solve such issues (Borden and Kenyon, 2014). Positive personal saving habit includes regular income management by putting money aside from the monthly payment, systematically spending money through planning, and designing the means of managing unexpected expenses (Pervinet, Reso & Terwnet, 2015). The savings level of households increases as the percentage of income amount increases.

Further, when individual income decreases, it tends to reduce both current consumption and saving. The work status of a household also determines its savings level. An employed individual saves more likely than an unemployed individual (Abdelkhalek, Bradley & Mitchell, 2010). Other than that, a household's behavior on overspending money should not be viewed as a remainder after current needs and wants have been met. It means the individuals will set aside a portion of their monthly income 10 - 20 percent. A person should establish a personal goal because it helps him save first rather than spend (Mohammad, A. & Gharleghi, 2015). As such, individuals will be more motivated to invest in different investment resources (Fisher, P. J., 2010)

In summary, financial behavior is the demeanor of the households that dictates the outcome of their future. The more the families improve their financial behavior, the more they'll get what the families desire. It means that the more they manage their finances, such as saving a portion of every income and invest in the right investment vehicle; it will resort to a better financial decision making. On the other hand, if the households are behaving recklessly regarding their finances and do not consider saving and investing shortly, the more chances the families will suffer from being ignorant of financial management. As a result, households are more likely to feel insecure about their wants and needs, which lead to depression. Hence, defining goals helps an individual distinguish and spotlight things that are generally essential to an individual (Lewis, 2010).

2.2 Financial Stress

Financial stress is more dominant in households that are earning a low income. These individuals struggle to live the standards of the community. This ideal is considered as a common stressor that leads them to work with their living situations that is why they tend to borrow money, ensure food security, and ascertain to pay their bills. These three factors are considered as a component of financial stress (Kramer et al., 2019).

Moreover, financial stress is the upsetting emotional inclination that an individual cannot fulfill his/her needs and wants. It also means that a household cannot manage the cost of life necessities and have inadequate assets to make a decent living (Satter, M. Y., 2017). It is the impression of the money related circumstance that is involved in the negative results. Additionally, it results to lower confidence, an undeniably negative point of view, and decreased psychological wellbeing, especially an expansion in gloom and aggression (Steen, A., & MacKenzie, D., 2013). It is also connected with declining physical wellbeing, such as sleep deprivation (Eurosystem Household Finance and Consumption Network, 2013). Further, it is frequently conceptualized as budgetary weight (costs which force a monetary value or battle), money related weakness (worries about the future economic circumstance), or a mix of these ideas, and can be available in low to prominent league salary families. Like neediness, financial stress is regularly connected with insufficient budgetary assets comparative with family needs (Hunter et al., 2014).

While money related pressure gives a few people and families significant issues, the experience of budgetary pressure for some could likewise be seen as a component of ordinary family unit planning and organizing (Marks, 2007). Budgetary pressure prompts getting cash. It is estimated that members often acquire money (Mason, C., & Wilson, R.M.S., 2000). On the other hand, a vast literature has examined food insecurity because of having a low income. However, among low-income families, millions are food secure. It is perhaps counter intuitive in so far as down and assumed to have insufficient resources to purchase necessities. There has been a way to avoid food insecurity, even in low households. The reason is to be good at financial management because the study shows that families that lack

information about financial management skills suffer from being food insecure (Dodo, M., 2017 & Ebissa, T., & Kassie, G., 2015).

Borrowing money sometimes soothes the families exceeding expenses when they cannot afford their families' daily costs. Because of this problem, they tend to borrow to aid and provide the essential commodities they need. However, there are some implications for why families or individuals borrow. One is that people tend to borrow even if it cost them a massive interest rate because they believe that by doing so, may preserve their assets for the future unexpected emergencies (Robb, C. & Woodyard, A., 2011). Otherwise, they save a part of its earnings for the future, even if their needs for its daily consumptions spike and the remaining payments drop its capability to finance it. Families stress over how to oversee income and keep up utilization while shuffling banks and the necessities of their all-inclusive informal community (Hunter W., Lort H. & Finn S., 2014). It appears prone to have ramifications for emotional wellness, food uncertainty, and homegrown maltreatment that are not recorded in the current studies (Johnson, E., & Sherraden, M. S., 2006).

Likewise, financial stress prompted unpaid bills, and over the long haul, youths were more discerning on their folks' social and monetary undertakings. They become more mindful of the family's financial assets' deficiency and think about the cut-off points (Haslam, D. M., & Burke, K., 2018). These force them on thinking the possibilities and or being antagonism on externalizing issues. Other than that, the monetary soundness of urban communities relies upon monetarily secure inhabitants (Marks, G. N., 2007.. At the point when families have next to zero reserve funds and experience a disturbance in their pay or costs, bills might be missed and outcomes is unfavourable (Nepl, Senia, and Donnellan, 2016).

In San Francisco, there are expected 170,000 families that don't have savings or are considered monetarily uncertain (Kasmir, T., 2010). It was proposed by numerous creators that to ease the said financial weakness which prompts unpaid bills, they suggest that the neighbourhood government must offer budgetary instructing, directing, and inventive the employments of innovation to help fabricate occupants' money related prosperity, including reserve funds systems. (Abdelkhalek J., Bradley U. & Mitchell O., 2010). They likewise propose to coordinate budgetary mediations, for example, to assist occupants with reimbursing rent and utility obligations into different projects to meet individuals where they are (Parcia, R. O., & Estimo, E. T. (2017). In conclusion, make sparing, simple through boosted programs that coordinate assets to assist occupants with building a crisis investment funds pad and climb the monetary stepping stool (Elliott and Kalesh, 2017).

In summary, financial stress is an emotional wonder. Two people in a similar fiscal circumstance may have various degrees of money related to stress (Lewis, N., 2010). Money-related conduct often speaks to as explicit conduct, for example, crises and retirement and staying away from a lot of obligations. Most exploration of the negative impact of budgetary behavior has been founded on the family stress model. As indicated by this model, pay by implication influences guardians' mental misery (e.g., sorrow) and makes between parental clash because of sentiments of money related strain or stress, for instance, not having the option to get by, concerns and shaky about the family's budgetary circumstance (Gutman, McLoyd, and Tokoyawa, 2005).

2.3 Correlation between Measures

There is a significant relationship between the two variables- financial behavior and financial stress. Financial behavior relative to financial stress among households relies on the impact of financial stress, whether positive or negative, in the family. It determines the person's reactions to how financially able they are in the community (Hayhoe et al., 2000). It means that financial behavior pertains to the capability to capture the understanding of the overall impacts of financial decisions on one's (i.e., person, family, community, country) circumstances. That makes the right decisions related to cash management, credit, saving, and investment management opportunities for budget plan (Ponnet, 2014). It has general implications towards adulthood as they extend throughout the family stage up for later life and determine the individual lifelong financial outcome (Eccles et al., 2013).

Many authors agreed that stress, especially financial stress brought about by poor monetary conduct, can negatively affect parental emotional wellness, resulting in ramifications for youngsters and teenagers' prosperity (Gutter & Copur, 2011). The most examination led to date on the negative impact of money related weight on guardians and kids founded on the family stress model created. This model places that stresses and instabilities over the family's money related

The Influence of Financial Behavior towards the Household's Financial Stress

circumstance regularly produce mental pain among guardians, similar to sentiments of sorrow. The model predicts that this mental pain prompts problematic or troublesome nurturing practices in its all-encompassing structure even in youngsters (Conger, Conger, and Martin, 2010).

The American Psychological Association (APA) concluded that 72 percent of Americans are stressed about money, at least occasionally and 22 percent feel incredibly stressed about their finances. It is significant because of financial stress associates with health problems like depression and sleep problems. With the rising cost of living, many Americans are feeling the crunch of financial stress (Bandura A., (1982). The result also revealed that financial literacy affecting good economic behavior plays a crucial role in lessening an individual's financial stress (Ebissa, T., & Kassie, G, 2015).

Moreover, to increase the individual's financial wellbeing within communities, they should manifest positive financial behaviour and to have good financial behavior, an individual must have good financial literacy (Menard, 2019). Basic financial literacy leads to good financial behavior, helps people become self-sufficient, and can substantially achieve financial stability. It includes saving money, distinguishing the difference between wants and needs, managing a budget, paying their bills, buying a home, paying for college, and planning for retirement (Rooij, M., Lusardi A., & Alessie, R., 2011). Financial literacy also empowers people to enhance their financial behavior. Without budgetary instruction, anything that looks like credit, loan costs, or ventures are scaring and departing people off guard. It additionally diminishes their money related feeling of anxiety. When individuals are knowledgeable in the condition of their funds, they have the data they have to make a move, change their speculation portfolio, or proceed with their present procedure (Horioka, C. & Watanabe, W., 1997).

The initial presentation and discussion of various literature works had helped bring into focus the importance of financial behavior and financial stress among households. The literature presented had also helped the researchers realize that financial stress has a significant impact on households' financial behavior. Furthermore, this research may bring explicit knowledge to households to handle the on their financial constraints.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the proposition of Hayhoe et al. (2000). They stated that financial behavior decreases the person's financial stress. Moreover, financial behavior relies on the impact of financial stress, whether positive or negative, on a person. Financial behavior determines the person's reactions as to how financially able they are in the community. It includes how the person's power of influences, capacity to employ human resources, and buy goods for their own family.

Hilgert, Hogarth & Beverly (2003) also explained that financial behavior arises because of the differences in financial resources in the behavioral hierarchy. This study suggests that an individual should know about cash management, credit management, savings management, and investment management to improve financial behavior. These factors have a severe impact on a household's life and affect their financial stability. Moreover, financial stress affects the physical and psychological well-being of individuals' performance. It also reflects the low-income families' struggle with the reality of financial constraints on their daily lives (Kramer et al., 2019).

2.5 Conceptual framework

Figure 1 shows the Conceptual Framework of the study and presents the Independent variable: *financial behaviour* that has four indicators: cash management, credit management, savings management, and investment management. In this study, *cash management* refers to the planning pattern of the household regarding their increasing wealth. Second, *credit management* talks about how to balance the household debt. Third, *savings management* broadens the understanding of the process to save money and its best effect. Lastly, *investment management* pertains to the individual's skill to manage or increase current assets' profitability.

The dependent variable is financial stress with the following indicators: borrowing money, food insecurity, and paying bills. First, *borrowing* pertains to the household's nature of borrowing; Second, *food insecurity* refers to how capable the households produces nutritious food on the table and secure health stability; Third, *paying bills* refer to the ability of the households to cover financial emergencies and paying monthly or unexpected bills.

Figure 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study consumptions.

2.6 Significance of the Study

The findings of this study enable to intensify the understanding of financial behaviour and financial stress among the family units in Tagum City. This study will also promote excellent financial behavior practices that certainly can affect the financial stress of the household. In the same way it will enable to help the families in Tagum City especially in the three largest barangay: Barangay Apokon, Barangay Visayan Village, and Barangay San Miguel to to balance their finances and plan an effective solution to improve their efficiency. It will eventually benefit the financial management students in general as they will gain ideas on how does financial behaviour would affect the financial stress. Moreover, the study's findings may provide future researchers a starting point and give a useful hint on expanding the research coverage in terms of the survey variables.

2.7 Definition of Terms

To better understand the terminologies used in the study, the following terms are defined operationally.

Financial Behavior. In this study, this pertains to cash management, credit management, savings, and investment management among households in Tagum City.

Financial Stress. Conceptually, it is defined as the unpleasant feeling of an individual whom unable to meet financial freedom and oftentimes involve themselves into cases like borrowing money, food insecurity, and paying bills among households in Tagum City.

III. METHOD

This chapter presents the method used, research design, research instrument, data gathering procedure, data gathering and data collection, and the statistical tool used in the data analysis.

3.1 Research Design

Quantitative non-experimental research design utilizing correlational technique was employed in this study design to gather data, ideas, information and facts of assessing the extent to which variables are correlated to each other. Usually, this means the non-experimental researcher must depend on correlations, surveys or case studies, and can't demonstrate a true cause-and-effect relationship. Quantitative non-experimental research design is empirical, using numeric and quantifiable data. The conclusions are based on experimentation and on objective and systematic observations (Belli, 2011).

Correlation research involved the collections of the data in order to decide to what level of relationship exist between two factors. It is a strategy for inquire about in which you have at least two quantitative factors from a similar gathering of subjects, and you are attempting to decide whether there is a connection between the two factors (Waters, 2010). The survey deals on quantitative data about the said phenomenon. The quantitative aspect is an appropriate schedule for gathering the data designed for the target respondents to answer the questions. The process of gathering the data was based through the use of questionnaire. The focus of the study is to determine the influence of financial behaviour towards the financial stress among households in Tagum City.

3.2 Research Locale

The findings of this study are specific to the context of financial behaviour and financial stress among households of Tagum City. The respondents are purposively identified coming from the three largest Barangay in Tagum City; these are Brgy. Apokon, Brgy. San Miguel and Brgy. Visayan Village. The extension and the example constrained the likelihood of the general materialness of the discoveries. The possibility for the general applicability of the findings was limited by scope, and the sample.

Accordingly, even though there could be common features, the findings may not have general applicability to other systems. Presented in figure 2 is the Map of the Philippines in Tagum City, in which the municipality of Tagum City province of Davao del Norte is located in Region XI. Moreover, presented in figure 2 is the vicinity map of the respondents in which the businesses are located in the city of Tagum. It is a 1st class city and capital of the Davao del Norte, Philippines. Tagum City, the capital of the province of Davao Del Norte, was formally created into an element city on March 7, 1998. Settled 55 kilometres north of Davao city, it's among the quickest growing towns in Region XI. It's a vast expanse of 19 580 hectares. In an exceedingly study conducted by the Asian Institute of Management, Tagum City was graded Among the 20th most viable city to try and do business within the country. The town is found 55 kilometers north of Davao city, the most economical and place of Region XI job. It takes concerning one hour and 30 minutes' visit Davao city. The city lies between 7°26' N latitude and 125°48' E line of longitude. It's bounded by the Municipalities of the national capital, New Corella, and Mawab on the north, Maco on the east, and B.E. Dujali on the west. Carmen lies on its southwestern borders, whereas it faces the Davao Gulf on the south.

3.3 Population and Sample

Purposive sampling technique was used to determine the participants. The study's subjects were the head of the family, and the respondents were the 150 households of the three largest Barangay in Tagum City: 50 participants are coming from Brgy. Apokon; 50 participants from Brgy. San Miguel; and 50 participants from Brgy. Visayan village. The studies were collected accordingly to determine the financial behavior and financial stress among households in Tagum City. This study was conducted for the S.Y 2019-2020.

3.4 Distribution of Respondents

Respondents	Sample	Percentage
Brgy. Apokon	50	33.33%
Brgy. San Miguel	50	33.33%
Brgy. Visayan Village	50	33.33%
Total	150	100%

3.5 Research Instrument

The researcher-made questionnaire was used as the instrument for this study, which the researchers personally constructed. It was used to gather relevant data needed using concise statements to provide the respondents with a prior understanding of the course. The researcher has created a questionnaire that is simple and concise that the proponents could easily understand. After distributing questionnaires through google form, the researchers generated the result of survey for the analysis and interpretation of the data.

Figure 2. Map of the Philippines Highlighting in Tagum City.

The Influence of Financial Behavior towards the Household's Financial Stress

In evaluating the financial behavior among household in Tagum City, the five orderable gradations with their respective range of means and description were considered:

Range Equivalent	Description	Interpretation
4.30-5.00	Very High	This means that the level of Financial behaviour among households in Tagum City is very much observed.
3.50-4.20	High	This means that the level of Financial behavior among households in Tagum City is much observed.
2.70-3.40	Moderate	This means that the level of Financial behavior among households in Tagum City is moderately observed.
1.90-2.60	Low	This means that the level of Financial behaviour among households in Tagum City is less observed.
1.00-1.80	Very Low	This means that the level of Financial behaviour among households in Tagum City is not observed at all.

The second set of a survey questionnaire in the household is financial stress with three indicators; borrowing money, food security, and paid bills. To determine the level of financial stress among family and the following parameter limits are to be used:

Range Equivalent	Description	Interpretation
4.30-5.00	Very High	This means that the level of Financial behaviour among households in Tagum City is very much experienced.
3.50-4.20	High	This means that the level of Financial behavior among households in Tagum City is much experienced.
2.70-3.40	Moderate	This means that the level of Financial behavior among households in Tagum City is moderately experienced.
1.90-2.60	Low	This means that the level of Financial behaviour among households in Tagum City is less experienced.
1.00-1.80	Very Low	This means that the level of Financial behaviour among households in Tagum City is not experienced at all.

3.6 Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers constructed the questionnaire that was submitted to the evaluators for corrections and suggestions. After which, it was distributed to the respondents through google form after the permission given. Right after the respondents have answered all the questions, the data gathered were tabulated and analyzed. Lastly is the interpretation of the result after the data has been calculated.

3.7 Statistical Treatment of the Data

The data gathered was tallied, tabulated, interpreted, and analyzed using the following statistical tools:

Mean. This statistical tool will be used to determine the level of financial behavior and financial stress among among households in Tagum City

Pearson r. This statistical tool will determine if there is a significant relationship between financial behavior and financial stress among households in Tagum City.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis. This statistical tool was used to determine if there are financial behavior domains that significant influence and financial stress.

IV. RESULTS

Presented in this chapter are the data and the result of the study. Tables are arranged in the following subheading: Level of Financial Behavior among family units; Level of Financial Stress among family units in Tagum City; Significant Relationship between Financial Behavior and Financial Stress among family units in Tagum City; and Regression Analysis of the Financial Behavior and Financial Stress among Household in Tagum City.

4.1 Level of Financial Behavior among Household's in Tagum City

Shown in table 1 is the level of financial behavior among households in Tagum City with an overall mean of 3.84 with a standard deviation of 0.62, which is described as high. It means that the respondent's response to the financial behavior among households in Tagum City is much observed.

Among the indicators, cash management obtained the highest mean of 3.91 with a standard deviation of 0.68, which has the descriptive equivalent of much observed. It is followed by credit management with a mean of 3.88 with a standard deviation of 0.67 and is described as high. Third, savings management has a mean of 3.85 with a standard deviation of 0.75 and is described as high; lastly, the lowest indicator is investment management with a mean of 3.62 and a standard deviation of 0.71, also described as high.

Table 1. Level of Financial Behavior among Household in Tagum City

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Cash Management	3.91	0.68	High
Saving Management	3.85	0.75	High
Credit Management	3.88	0.67	High
Investment Management	3.62	0.71	High
Overall	3.84	0.62	High

The primary indicator of the financial behavior with the highest mean is on *Cash Management*. It indicates that households were able to keep records of their cash transaction, which leads them to maintain a well-organized cash budget plan. Likewise, they monitor their cash outflows or expenses from time to time to project immediate expenses and avoid cash shortage. Lastly, households were able to stick with their budget plan and prevent overspending.

Regarding *credit management*, the respondent obtained the second highest mean score, showing a favourable response in dealing with their borrowings. It entails that the households determine first the credit amount needed, credit terms, interest rates, and the credit purpose before incurring debt. Hence, they prevent unfavourable obligation to avoid a possible financial problems. Households also make sure to keep on track regularly on their credit transactions and always set a reserve fund.

The Influence of Financial Behavior towards the Household's Financial Stress

Meanwhile, *savings management* obtained the third highest mean score. The respondents save out of their income and create emergency funds to cover unexpected expenses. They also save for retirement purposes and for long-term goals such as education, home, and car. They make sure to have enough cash available in their savings account and keep a portion of their income every month.

Subsequently, *investment management* with the lowest mean implies that the respondents much observed the items indicated. It also suggests that the respondents invest in different investments to diversify their portfolio. As to investment, they capitalize in financial products that they have fully understand. Lastly, they look for new investment opportunities such as investing in stocks, bonds, and mutual funds.

4.2 Level of Financial Stress among Household Household's in Tagum City

Table 2 shows the level of financial stress among households with an overall mean of 2.78, with a standard deviation of 0.53, described as moderate. It means that the level of financial stress among households in Tagum city is moderately experienced.

Among the indicators, *borrowing money* obtained the highest mean of 3.00 with a standard deviation of 0.65 described as moderate, followed by *paying bills* with a mean of 2.73 and a standard deviation of 0.74 described as moderate and *food insecurity* 2.61 with a standard deviation of 0.74 described as low.

The respondents' primary indicator of the financial stress with the highest mean is on *borrowing money* it has a descriptive equivalent of moderately experienced; this means that they do have a repayment plan for debt borrowing hence, households cannot really avoid excessive borrowing and sometimes incurred credit with high-interest rates. Lastly, the respondents used to borrow money to cover up current debts and necessities to fulfil the financial problem and survive until the next payoff.

Table 2. Level of Financial Stress among Households in Tagum City

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Borrowing Money	3.00	0.65	Moderate
Food Insecurity	2.61	0.74	Low
Paying Bills	2.73	0.74	Moderate
Overall	2.78	0.53	Moderate

The next indicator with the highest mean is *paying bills*, the respondent's responses were moderately experienced. It implies that the household pay bills on time because they allocate their income properly before the due date. However, some families incurred surcharges due to emergencies but in a minimal situation. Nevertheless, they suffer financial turmoil or encounter financial difficulties rarely.

Finally, the lowest mean is the *Food Insecurity*; this explains that the household is not suffering from getting nutritious food and buying all necessities they needed on time. They can certainly afford to purchase healthy foods daily even if they have minimum income. The households make sure that they can sustain proper nutrition for all of the family despite having some financial constraints.

4.3 Significant Relationship between Financial Behavior and Financial Stress

This study's primary purpose is to determine whether financial behaviour has a significant relationship with the household's financial stress. Pearson r was used to determine the correlation between the two variables. Shown in Table 3 is the result of the significant relationship between financial behavior and financial stress. It reveals that financial behavior versus financial stress has an r-value of 0.244**, which is significant. The result is due to the p-value of 0.003, which is lower than the 0.05 level of significance. It leads to the decision that the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between financial behavior and financial stress, is rejected. This further means that there is a relationship between two variables correlated. Based on research on the relationship between financial behavior and

The Influence of Financial Behavior towards the Household's Financial Stress

financial stress, it has been evident that households' financial behaviour influences their financial stress. Therefore, the correlation demonstrates that when financial behaviour is much observed, the financial stress is moderately experienced by the family units in Tagum City.

Table 3. The significant relationship between financial behavior and financial stress among households in Tagum City

Variables	Mean	SD	r - value	p-value
Financial Behavior	3.84	0.62		
Financial Stress	2.78	0.53	0.244**	0.003

*Significant at 0.05 significance level

4.4 Regression Analysis of the influence of Financial Behavior and Financial Stress

Data shown in Table 4 are the regression coefficients that test the significant influence of the overall financial behavior and financial stress among households in Tagum City. Using the Multiple Linear Regression Analysis, the data revealed that the impact of financial behavior towards financial stress among household in Tagum City has an F-value of 3.919** and a corresponding p-value of 0.005. The R^2 of 0.098 implies that 9.8% of the factors that influences the financial stress are influenced by the financial behavior while the remaining 90.2% are influence by the other related factors. The cash management indicator has a beta of 0.258 and a corresponding p-value of 0.059, which means that cash management, has no significant influence on financial stress. Also, *savings management* has a beta of 0.156 and a p-value of 0.269, which means that it has no significant influence on the financial stress. Whereas, *credit management* has a beta of -0.249 and a p-value of 0.070, which means that it has also no significant influence on financial stress. Lastly, *investment management* has a beta of 0.118 and a p-value of 0.279, which means that it has also no significant effect on financial stress.

Table 4. Regression Analysis for Variables Predicting Financial Stress among household

Brand (indicators)	B (Understand-ardized Coefficients)	β (Standardized Coefficients)	t - value	p-value
(Constant)	1.298			
Cash Management	0.391	0.258	1.906	0.059
Saving Management	0.215	0.156	1.109	0.269
Credit Management	-0.384	-0.249	-1.827	0.070
Investment Management	0.171	0.118	1.086	0.279
Dependent Variable:				
R = 0.312		$R^2 = 0.098$		
F-value = 3.919**		P-value = 0.005		

**p<0.0

V. DISCUSSION

The data on financial behavior and financial stress on Tagum City households are presented in this chapter. The discussion is based on the findings that appeared in the previous section.

The Influence of Financial Behavior towards the Household's Financial Stress

5.1 Level of Financial Behavior of the Households in Tagum City

The respondents' level of financial behavior in Tagum City is high. This means that different households' financial behavior is much observed. This further means that Tagum City households are manifested all the items under cash management, savings management, credit management, and investment management.

The primary indicator of the financial behavior that has the highest mean was on *Cash Management* that is very much observed among household in Tagum City, followed by *credit management* that is much observed among household in Tagum City, *savings management* that is much observed among household in Tagum City, and *investment management* that is much observed among household in Tagum City.

This result implies that the households in Tagum City observed proper cash allocation by budgeting current income to basic needs and wants. Also, they practice saving a portion of their income for emergency purposes. They also seek advice from experts to know about suitable investments to maximize their wealth. They moderately acquire credits so that they can achieve their financial objectives. This result aligns with the theory of Cox, Drew & Walter (2010), which stated that the attitude, beliefs, perception, and conscientious manner on spending boost their financial well-being. This means that a household with favorable financial behavior is less likely to suffer from financial burdens than less conscientious individuals.

5.2 Level of Financial Stress among Household in Tagum City

The overall mean of financial stress among households in Tagum City is moderate. This means that the financial stress of households in Tagum City is moderately experienced. This further means that the households in Tagum City moderately manifested all the items under borrowing money, paying bills, and food insecurity.

The main indicator of financial stress with the highest mean was on *borrowing money* that is described as high, followed by *paying bills* with a moderate descriptive equivalent, and *food insecurity* with low descriptive equivalent.

This result implies that households' financial stress in Tagum City is moderately experienced in all the items in the three indicators. Even though they have lower income levels, they are not totally suffering from successive borrowing of money; hence they practice proper allocation and implementation of the budget. Results also entail that households avoid overspending their current income to pay bills and avoid over dues or surcharges. By doing so, households are less likely to experience food insecurity; instead, they could sustain nutritious food for the family. The results are opposite of the theory of Kramer et al. (2019), which stated that financial stress is more dominant in households gaining with lower levels of income. It makes them struggle through living the standards set by the community involving them. This common stressor leads individuals to work with their living situations, and they tend to borrow money, have food insecurity, and delayed payments on bills, which are known to affect their physical and psychological stability.

5.3 Correlation between Financial Behavior and Financial Stress

The present study reveals a significant relationship between financial behavior and financial stress among households in Tagum City that lead to rejecting the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between the two variables. This implies that financial behavior significantly influences the financial stress of households in Tagum City. Moreover, Hayhoe et al. (2000) stated that an individual's financial behavior relies on financial stress, whether positive or negative, on a person. Financial behavior determines the person's reactions to how financially stable they were in the community; it includes the person's power of influences, capacity to employ human resources, and buy goods for their own family.

5.4 Regression Analysis of Financial Behavior and Financial Stress among Households InTagum City

The regression coefficient tests the significant influence of households' overall financial behavior and financial stress in Tagum City. Using simple linear regression, the data revealed that financial behavior influenced financial stress among households in Tagum City. The overall results of financial behavior predict the financial stress among households in Tagum City. Thus, it can be repeatedly stated here that the hypothesis said no significant relationship between financial behavior and financial stress is rejected. Further, the data revealed that no domain significantly influences financial stress among financial behavior indicators (cash management, credit management, savings management, and investment management). As stated in the previous section of the study, the relationship's significance conformed to the

The Influence of Financial Behavior towards the Household's Financial Stress

theories being espoused. It could be repetitively mentioned in this section that financial behavior determines the person's reactions to how financially stable they were in the community; it includes the person's power of influences, capacity to employ human resources, and buying goods for their own family (Hayhoe et al., 2000).

VI. Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, conclusions are drawn in this section. Financial behavior among households in Tagum City, Davao del Norte is high for cash management, saving management, credit management, and investment management. The overall mean of financial behavior among households in Tagum City is high. This further means that the respondent's response to the items of financial behavior is much observed. The level of financial stress among households in Tagum City is moderate for borrowing money, low for food insecurity and moderate for paying bills, and the overall mean of moderate for the level of financial behavior among households in Tagum City. This means that all measures described in financial stress among households in Tagum City, items were moderately experienced. There is a significant relationship between financial behavior and financial stress among households in Tagum City, and there is no domain in financial behavior that best predict financial stress.

VII. Recommendation

Based on the findings and conclusion drawn, the following recommended actions were made: Households in Tagum City may lower down the level of their financial stress through financial awareness on their behaviour or attitude towards handling cash flows and financial budgets. As to investment, they may focus on investing in financial products that they are knowledgeable about. It also recommends that households should capitalize in different investments that are appropriate for them. To attain this, they shall attend on financial seminars to advance their knowledge on investments. Lastly, they have to look for new investment opportunities, such as investing in insurance, stocks, bonds, and mutual funds. Lastly, it may provide future researchers with a starting point on expanding the research coverage in terms of the study's variables.

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